

**BIOremediation systems exploiting SYnergies
for improved removal of Mixed pOllutants**

Deliverable D7.1

**Visual identity, website and
social media accounts**

Deliverable information

Responsible Partner:	EXELISIS
Work Package	WP7
Author(s):	EXELISIS
Contributing Partner(s):	IDENER
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Project Profile

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Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-10
Number	101060211
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- Confirm that all their individual contributions to this deliverable are genuine and their own work or the work of their teams working in the Project, except where is explicitly indicated otherwise.
- Have followed the required conventions in referencing the thoughts, ideas and texts made outside the Project.

Executive Summary

This deliverable is linked with activities performed under WP7 of the BIOSYSMO project, under the Grant Agreement Number 101060211, and in particular activities under Task 7.1 “Project communication channels and tools” led by EXELISIS. This document refers to the setup of the BIOSYSMO communication tools including logo creation, corporate identity, templates, presentation, project website structure and development which will continuously be updated (news, press releases, newsletters, digital material) and improved, as well as the social media platforms and maintenance.

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1 What is the project about?

BIOSYSMO is a 48-month project that proposes the formulation and application of a computational model-driven framework for the design and improvement of synergetic biosystems for removal of mixed contaminants from polluted soils, sediments and (ground)water. These biosystems will comprise combinations of bacteria, fungi and plants containing the natural or engineered pathways required for pollutants degradation and identified based on a computationally-assisted analysis.

BIOSYSMO will take advantage of the high natural microbial diversity by screening samples from polluted sites and locations affected by diffuse pollution to identify natural microorganisms already present and able to metabolize the target pollutants. The search will be expanded to microorganisms previously identified and characterized by applying data mining tools to genomic and metagenomic data available in public repositories. Then construction and optimization of synergistic biosystems will follow which will be applied in conventional (phytoremediation, biopile, bioaugmentation) and innovative (BES, hybrid BES-phytoremediation) bioremediation approaches optimized for the treatment of mixtures of pollutants in soil, sediments and water.

2 Visual Identity

The visual identity of the project is an important aspect, as it includes all the graphical information that differentiates the project from others. In this section the logo and colour guidelines, as well as the templates, used for presentations, deliverables, agenda, participant list and minutes of meetings, following the visual identity of the project will be included.

2.1 Logo and colour guidelines

In Figure 1 the official logo of the project is presented. The logo was uniquely designed to match the BIOSYSMO concept and will support project's easy recognition. It is aimed at conveying the project's message and helps to reach the target audience. Detailed guidelines are shared with the project consortium on how to include the official logo as it is important to follow the project's identity. Moreover, Figures 2-5 present the font that was used, the colours, and the variation of colours and logo.

Figure 1: Project Logo

LOGO VARIATIONS

FONT

Figure 2: Project Logo Variations

Figure 3: Project Font

COLOURS

Figure 4: Project Colors in RGB and CMYK

LOGO COLOUR VARIATIONS

Figure 5: Logo colours variations

2.2 Templates

In this section the designed templates for the presentation of the project, the Deliverables Templates, the Agenda Template, the List of Participants, and the Meeting Minutes, that the partners and the coordinator will use during the project, are presented.

2.2.1 Presentation template

The presentation consists of a title slide and closure slide, one slide for separating the sections, and several slides serving the presentation of tasks overview, task description, interconnection of tasks and deliverables and milestones lists.

WP No. & title
 BIOSYSMO Kick-off Meeting
 October 3rd, 2022 – Online
 [WP leader]
 [Presenter]

Title slide

WP OVERVIEW

	Partner	Effort per partner
Title:		
WP Leader:		
WP participants:		
Duration:		
Total effort in PMs:		

Overview slide

POSITIONING IN THE PROJECT

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4
WP1: Field sampling and characterisation of polluted and treated samples	M1-4M2			
WP2: Computational tools for biosystems design and representation	M1-4M6			
WP3: Development and optimisation of conceptual and detailed biosystems	M1-4M3			
WP4: Application of improved biosystems and optimisation of the bioremediation strategy	M12-4M6			
WP5: Field studies, validation and roadmap for wider implementation	M12-4M8			
WP6: Environmental, socio-economic, risk and regulatory assessment	M12-4M7			
WP7: Communication, dissemination and exploitation	M1-4M5			
WP8: Project management	M1-4M4			

Timeline slide

INTERACTION WITH OTHER WPs

```

    graph TD
      WPXX1[WPXX (Task X.X)] --- WPXX2[WPXX (Task X.X)]
      WPXX1 --- WPXX3[WPXX (Task X.X)]
      WPXX1 --- WPXX4[WPXX (Task X.X)]
      WPXX1 --- WPXX5[WPXX (Task X.X)]
      WPXX1 --- WPXX6[WPXX (Task X.X)]
  
```

WPs slide

DELIVERABLES

No.	Description	Type	Leader	Co-leads	Status
ED	Initial report on work status and progress	Report	EDNER	M5	Task started (M4)
ED-1	Task report from Task 2.2.1.1: Develop the initial 2D model of the polluted and treated samples and represent it in a computational tool (CFD)	Report	EDNER	M5	Task started (M4)
ED-2	Task report from Task 2.2.1.2: Develop the initial 2D model of the polluted and treated samples and represent it in a computational tool (CFD)	Report	EDNER	M5	Task started (M4)
ED-3	Task report from Task 2.2.1.3: Develop the initial 2D model of the polluted and treated samples and represent it in a computational tool (CFD)	Report	EDNER	M5	Task started (M4)
ED-4	Task report from Task 2.2.1.4: Develop the initial 2D model of the polluted and treated samples and represent it in a computational tool (CFD)	Report	EDNER	M5	Task started (M4)
ED-5	Task report from Task 2.2.1.5: Develop the initial 2D model of the polluted and treated samples and represent it in a computational tool (CFD)	Report	EDNER	M5	Task started (M4)

Deliverables slide

OVERVIEW OF TASKS

Section slide

Task slide

Empty slide

Closure slide

Figure 6: Presentation Slides Template

2.2.2 Deliverable template

Figure 7 refers to the Deliverable Template that will be used by all partners throughout the 48M project.

Deliverable D7.1
Title

Deliverable information	
Responsible Partner:	
Work Package:	
Author(s):	
Contributing Partner(s):	
Dissemination Level:	
Type:	
Due Date:	
Submission Date:	
Version:	

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Executive Summary

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4 Conclusions
5 References

Figure 7: Deliverable Template pages

BIOSYSMO Meeting
List of participants

No.	Entity	Name	Signature

No.	Entity	Name	Signature

Figure 9: List of participants template

2.2.5 Meeting minutes

Meeting minutes help the organisers of an event to note down the items discussed, the actions points and issues that need to be resolved, as well as any upcoming meeting scheduled.

X M Project Coordination Meeting

Date: _____

Time: _____

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Partners

Beneficiary	Country	Attendance
IDENER RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT AGRUPACION DE INTERES ECONOMICO	IDE ES	<input type="checkbox"/>
UNIVERSIDAD DE BURGOS	UBU ES	<input type="checkbox"/>
INSTITUT JOZEF STEFAN	JSI SI	<input type="checkbox"/>
ACONDICIONAMIENTO TARRASENSE ASSOCIACION	LEITAT ES	<input type="checkbox"/>
COMMUNAUTE D' UNIVERSITES ET ETABLISSEMENTS UNIVERSITE BOURGOGNE - FRANCHIE - COMTE	UBPC FR	<input type="checkbox"/>
BLUE SYNERGY SL	BSY ES	<input type="checkbox"/>
CENTRO INTERDISCIPLINAR DE INVESTIGACAO MARINHA E AMBIENTAL	CIIMAR PT	<input type="checkbox"/>
UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM ES	<input type="checkbox"/>
AXIA INNOVATION UG	AXIA DE	<input type="checkbox"/>
CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	CNRS FR	<input type="checkbox"/>
TAUW GMBH	TAUW DE	<input type="checkbox"/>
EXELISIS IKE	EXE EL	<input type="checkbox"/>

Funded by the European Union Meeting Minutes Project Coordination Meeting, MM00171 2 of 5

BIOremediation systems exploiting SYnergieS for improved removal of Mixed pOllutants

List of participants

Participating Organization	Participant Name

BIOremediation systems exploiting SYnergieS for improved removal of Mixed pOllutants

Meeting Minutes

WP1:

Update:

Next Actions:

WP2:

Update:

Next Actions:

WP3:

Update:

Next Actions:

BIOremediation systems exploiting SYnergieS for improved removal of Mixed pOllutants

Meeting Minutes

WP1:

Update:

Next Actions:

WP2:

Update:

Next Actions:

WP3:

Update:

Next Actions:

BIOremediation systems exploiting SYnergieS for improved removal of Mixed pOllutants

Meeting Minutes

WP1:

Update:

Next Actions:

WP2:

Update:

Next Actions:

WP3:

Update:

Next Actions:

Figure 10: Meeting minutes template

3 Website

The website will be used as the primary interface with the public interested in the work, actions, progress, and outcomes of the project.

The website link is: www.biosysmo.eu

The theme on which the BIOSYSMO project website was developed and made the necessary edits to represent project's identity and scope, is Consultio.

The website contains information about the objectives of the project, the concept, the methodology, the technologies, the outcomes, partners' details, list of news and events, dissemination materials that will be developed during the project and are available for downloading, public deliverables, publications, links to social media platforms to follow and like the project's pages, newsletter subscription, clustering projects, and contact information. In this section the navigation bar, footer, home page, and all tabs one by one are visualised.

3.1 Website target audiences

The website is the project's showcase and it is aiming at spreading and increasing public awareness of the project by providing visual and easy to comprehend information about the concept of the project. The project website (www.biosysmo.eu) is the primary information source for the targeted audiences. The target audiences are the following:

- **End-users: environmental consultancy and engineering companies, polluting industries, plant breeders and producers, microbial inoculant producers**
- **Scientific community**
- **Policy makers, public authorities**
- **Environmental NGOs**
- **Students, early-stage researchers and new generation of workers**
- **Public and society at large**

The purpose of the website is **to create awareness** of the project through communication activities (starting at M1 and continuing until the end of the project) and to **disseminate the results** of the project to targeted relevant stakeholders (starting with the first results and continuing after the end of the project).

Analytics of the website such as number of visitors, downloads, most clickable page and more will be used.

3.2 Website navigation bar

In Figure 11 the navigation bar is organised as follows:

- **Home** tab that contains a summary of the project and the content of the website
- **In Brief** tab contains subtabs the concept of the project, the objectives and the expected outcomes

- **Meet the team** tab contains information about the coordinator and the partners
- **Research activities** tab contains the workplan presenting the work packages, a small description providing more information on them, the project's methodology, the applications that the project will target and the field studies where the project technologies will be tested and validated
- **Media** tab contains news, events, press releases and newsletters that will be continuously updated during the 48M project.
- **Digital Library** tab is aimed to share with the public D&C material including the logo, qr code, presentation template, poster, flyer, roll-up, lanyard, folder, publications, and public deliverables
- **Clustering** tab contains relevant projects, that share similar technologies as BIOSYSMO
- **Contact** tab contains a form and all necessary information for contacting the project coordinator, while it also presents links of the social media of the project

Figure 11: Navigation bar of the BIOSYSMO website

3.3 Website footer

The footer of the website (Figure 12) contains newsletter subscription, contact info, projects details, the mandatory EU logo and funding statement, links for the social profiles and privacy policy.

Figure 12: Footer of BIOSYSMO website

The privacy policy can be found at the bottom of the footer, where procedures on personal data processing, and data collection and protection, among others, are agreed.

We are very delighted that you have shown interest in our enterprise. Data protection is of a particularly high priority for the management of the EXELISIS. The use of the Internet pages of the EXELISIS is possible without any indication of personal data; however, if a data subject wants to use special enterprise services via our website, processing of personal data could become necessary. If the processing of personal data is necessary and there is no statutory basis for such processing, we generally obtain consent from the data subject.

The processing of personal data, such as the name, address, e-mail address, or telephone number of a data subject shall always be in line with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and in accordance with the country-specific data protection regulations applicable to the EXELISIS. By means of this data protection declaration, our enterprise would like to inform the general public of the nature, scope, and purpose of the personal data we collect, use and process. Furthermore, data subjects are informed, by means of this data protection declaration, of the rights to which they are entitled.

Figure 13: Privacy policy

3.4 Website pages

Figures of the structure of the website will follow.

Home page: On the top of the page the navigation bar appears, using a structure that is commonly used, with the project's logo. Then 4 categories of impacts the project will make are described. Followingly, the concept idea is presented, the BIOSYSMO key elements, links to other website sections (including outcomes, technologies and sites) and latest news (Figure 14).

Figure 14: Full Home page

In Brief: A more detailed description of the project is given (Figure 15.a) while information is also given regarding the project's objectives (Figure 15.b) and outcomes (Figure 15.c).

What is BIOSYSMO?

BIOSYSMO is a 48-month action that will develop a computationally-assisted framework for designing and optimizing synergistic biosystems containing the required pathways and traits to achieve the most efficient degradation and sequestration of pollutant mixtures.

These biosystems will comprise combinations of bacteria, fungi and plants containing the natural or engineered pathways required for pollutants degradation and identified based on a computationally-assisted analysis. BIOSYSMO will take advantage of the high natural microbial diversity by screening samples from polluted sites and locations affected by diffuse pollution to identify natural microorganisms already present and able to metabolize the target pollutants. The search will be expanded to microorganisms previously identified and characterized by applying data mining tools to genomic and metabolomic data available in public repositories.

The construction and optimization of synergistic biosystems will combine approaches based on:

- enhancing spatiotemporal (bacteria, fungi) interactions to achieving combinations with improved pollutant uptake and/or degradation;
- engineering bacteria for improved degradation and bioremediation, and plants (poorly tested) for improved microbial colonization and pollutant uptake;
- constructing artificial micro-structured consortia into aggregates and biofilms, containing all the required pathways for pollutant removal; and
- applying biotechnological systems (BES) as standalone or in hybrid systems

The constructed biosystems will be optimized for the treatment of mixtures of pollutants in soil, sediments and waters

through conventional (phytoremediation, biotrickle, bioaugmentation) and innovative (BES, hybrid BES-phytoremediation) bioremediation approaches

(a)

Major Objectives

Development & application

of a computational pipeline to improve the design and construction of synergistic bioremediation systems.

To design, enhance, apply & optimize
 synergistic systems for bioremediation and address of targeted mixed pollutants in water, soil and sediments

To perform

field studies and validation of selected bioremediation systems

To evaluate

the environmental, socio-economic, risk and regulatory aspects of the bioremediation methods

To effectively exploit & mainstream

the project results for increased impact

To collect and characterize

difficult samples from selected sites

(b)

The project unravels around the following two major impacts

Innovative biotechnology creating zero-pollution bio-based solutions

Outcome #1: Applying novel advances in computational and bioinformatics tools for accelerating and improving the design of synergistic biosystems that will be efficient for bioremediation and remediation of polluted soil, sediments and water.

Outcome #2: Innovative enhancement strategies, such as genetic engineering, BES, microbial engineering and microencapsulation, will be applied throughout and combined in novel hybrid systems. Moreover, the phytoremediation strategies developed offer additional applications for waste recycling.

Outcome #3: Providing bio-based knowledge on the interaction of, e.g., plant or microbial strains, with the media and within the bioremediation system. In addition, a systematic assessment of the bioremediation potential and low-impact analysis methods will be developed, tailored to the specific site requirements.

Outcome #4: The novel bioremediation methods will be validated within the framework of the project in lab conditions using real polluted matrices (i.e., in other bioremediation sites) using field bioremediation (FBS).

Outcome #5: Advanced assessments on LCA, ICC, water CA and Environmental Risk Assessment (ERA) will be applied to bioremediation and bioremediation processes. Moreover, the methodology will follow FAIR data principles, for storing data in open (e.g., ICDO, Zenodo) CA data, open contributing to the OADR mission.

Circular bio-based systems reversing climate change, restoring biodiversity & protecting air, water & soil quality

Outcome #6: New approaches for efficient bioremediation and resource recovery.

Outcome #7: Targeting to establish and restore natural ecosystems, design and develop highly sustainable, circular and reduce microbial contamination and provide viable solutions for pollution removal. But contrary will create an ecosystem that will support additional biodiversity.

Outcome #8: Developing biotechnologies that will be gentle with the environment while ensuring soil health and water quality and ensure environmental performance will be thoroughly assessed through and LCA/Environmental Risk Assessment.

Outcome #9: Optimizing the metabolic routes and synthetic pathways of biosystems to reduce consumption of water, nutrients or energy, ensuring the environmental footprint of bioremediation processes. Moreover, through an eco-friendly assessment and considerations of the benefits of the bioremediation processes will be provided, identifying possible pathways that maximize and using resources to avoid those, while the application of LCA will be greatly improved by the FAIR.

(c)

Figure 15: In Brief tab a. Concept page, b. Objectives, c. Outcomes

Meet the team: In this section, the coordinator and partners of the project are presented, including a small description of their actions and role during the project.

— It is a pleasure to work together

IDENER

IDENER I+D+i is a Spanish private research organization with expertise in the multidisciplinary field of Computational Science. The Bioinformatics Area of IDENER I+D+i investigates the development and application of computational tools such as mathematical modeling and simulation, data science, machine learning, process modeling and assessment and software engineering to biotechnology processes. The team has a strong track record in diverse fields of research such as molecular biology, chemical and environmental engineering and computational chemistry and biology.

Main role: Coordination; Big data analysis; machine learning techniques; genome-scale metabolic models.

Universidad de Burgos

UBU and the International Research Center in Critical Raw Materials for Advanced Industrial Technologies (ICRAM) is well-equipped for sustainability research approached from a multidisciplinary point of view with activities in optimization and resource efficiency and waste characterization, aimed to develop Circular Economy and sustainable solutions.

Main role: Development, optimization and application of bioprocesses for plant-based waste treatment; soil bioremediation.

Figure 16: Meet the team page

Research Activities: In this tab the work packages are presented with a visual diagram, followed by the methodology, the applications of the project and the field studies of the project.

WP1 WP2 WP3 WP4 WP5 WP6 WP7 WP8

Field sampling and characterization of polluted and treated samples

Leader: CIIMAR
Duration: M1-M42

This work package focuses on the collection and the characterization of samples from polluted sites aiming to optimize and validate bioremediation strategies. The activities include the analysis of different pollutants and the development of protocols and workflows across laboratories. LUMINO will be employed to target micropollutants. The microbial community in the polluted samples will be characterized and microorganisms with pollutant degradation potential will be identified. In addition, WP1 will develop a (bio)technological toolset for evaluation of bioremediation potential.

How we do it step by step

1. Integrated cross-referenced database

BIOSYSMO will register a vast amount of public data and information to identify candidate organisms or genes associated with tested bioremediation strategies and to select the most promising. Multiple mining techniques will be employed to automatically mine databases and identify candidates to identify pathways with unique patterns and independent activity of specific pollutants as well as their effect on gene expression. The integrated cross-referenced database will be also fed with the experimental microbial and plant characterization data obtained in BIOSYSMO. The data mining approach will focus on (I) genes with specific transporter pathways, (II) candidate genes or LAG with their existing gene connections, (III) genes with homologous activity, (IV) genes and plant genes that can improve pollutant uptake or degradation processes, and (V) other genes associated with plant susceptibility to microbe colonization.

2. Model-driven metabolic pathways reconstruction and analysis

Genomic Scale Models (GSM) will be employed to design suitable microbial communities for the degradation of specific and mixtures of pollutants. Model reactions to metabolic pathways of microbial communities, and essential metabolites to identify pathways with unique patterns and independent activity of specific pollutants as well as their effect on gene expression. The integrated cross-referenced database will be also fed with the experimental microbial and plant characterization data obtained in BIOSYSMO. The data mining approach will focus on (I) genes with specific transporter pathways, (II) candidate genes or LAG with their existing gene connections, (III) genes with homologous activity, (IV) genes and plant genes that can improve pollutant uptake or degradation processes, and (V) other genes associated with plant susceptibility to microbe colonization.

3. Experimental testing and design of biosystems

BIOSYSMO will select synergistic interactions within microbial communities as well as the interaction between microbes and plants. Different strategies (GEM) will be used for the design and development of these biosystems.

3.1. Endophyte-polar biosystems for soil phytoremediation

Endophytes enhance the plant host processing plant growth and health (e.g. nutrient use efficiency). Plant genes will be used to enhance the tolerance to selected molecules and environmental conditions. However, microbial

(a)

What's the use of BIOSYSMO

Application 1: Field Sampling/Characterization of polluted sites
This application focuses on the collection and the characterization of samples from polluted sites aiming to optimize and validate bioremediation strategies. The activities include the analysis of different pollutants and the development of protocols and workflows across laboratories. LUMINO will be employed to target micropollutants. The microbial community in the polluted samples will be characterized and microorganisms with pollutant degradation potential will be identified. In addition, WP1 will develop a (bio)technological toolset for evaluation of bioremediation potential.

Application 2: Integrated cross-referenced database
BIOSYSMO will register a vast amount of public data and information to identify candidate organisms or genes associated with tested bioremediation strategies and to select the most promising. Multiple mining techniques will be employed to automatically mine databases and identify candidates to identify pathways with unique patterns and independent activity of specific pollutants as well as their effect on gene expression. The integrated cross-referenced database will be also fed with the experimental microbial and plant characterization data obtained in BIOSYSMO. The data mining approach will focus on (I) genes with specific transporter pathways, (II) candidate genes or LAG with their existing gene connections, (III) genes with homologous activity, (IV) genes and plant genes that can improve pollutant uptake or degradation processes, and (V) other genes associated with plant susceptibility to microbe colonization.

Application 3: Experimental testing and design of biosystems
BIOSYSMO will select synergistic interactions within microbial communities as well as the interaction between microbes and plants. Different strategies (GEM) will be used for the design and development of these biosystems.

Application 4: Endophyte-polar biosystems for soil phytoremediation
Endophytes enhance the plant host processing plant growth and health (e.g. nutrient use efficiency). Plant genes will be used to enhance the tolerance to selected molecules and environmental conditions. However, microbial

(c)

Throughout Europe

Each biosystem developed in the project is oriented to target a specific pollution problem that needs a tailored-made approach. Several pollution sites have been selected so they are diverse in nature and representative of common and relevant pollution problems throughout Europe.

Additionally, the computationally-based pipeline developed under BIOSYSMO is expected to be applicable for other pollutants susceptible to be bioremediated, making the approach replicable in other situations. The Figure below illustrates the polluted sites and the approaches that BIOSYSMO will study.

(d)

Figure 17: Research Activities tab a. Workplan, b. Methodology, c. Applications, d. Field studies

Media: In this tab the news and events are included along with the Newsletters and Press Releases, which will be continuously updated/developed during the project.

Learn our latest news and events of the project

(a)

Read & Download Available news & more

Newsletter Magazines

Press Releases

(b)

Figure 18: Media tab a. News and Events, b. Newsletter and Press Releases

Digital Library: In this section all the downloadable content of the project can be found, including the logo, qr code, flyer, roll-up, poster, folder and lanyard, the publications that acknowledge the project and the public deliverables. These sections will continuously be updated during the project.

Figure 19: Digital Library a. D&C materials, b. Publications, c. Public deliverables

Clustering: In this page projects addressing relevant topics will be presented along with some information about their topic, title and a link to their official project website. This section will be enriched during the project implementation, as the clustering activities will progress.

Figure 20: Clustering page

Contact: In this page the contact form can be used to get in touch with the project coordinator through email, social media and in person.

Figure 21: Contact page

4 Social media platforms

In addition to the webpage, LinkedIn account and Twitter account have been developed for the BIOSYSMO project. These social media platforms have been selected as have the most active users between the age of 16 to 64 who keep up to date their news and current events¹. Therefore, these platforms can act as a medium to maximize dissemination/communication of the project results to a wide public audience, such as environmental consultancy and engineering companies, polluting industries, plant breeders and producers, microbial inoculant producers, scientists, students, as well the wider public that may be interested in learning another field.

Project partners are encouraged to visit, like and follow these accounts and communicate them to their professional and private networks. Access to the social media will be supported through the project webpage. The evaluation of the accessibility and efficiency of these accounts will be made on the basis of performance metrics, such as number of visits, followers, engagement, etc.

4.1 LinkedIn account

LinkedIn is the world's largest professional networking platform². It is also one of the most influential social media networks, with 756 million members. Users of this platform keep in touch with associations, companies, businesses, universities etc. to learn more and reading news about their fields of interest.

The BIOSYSMO LinkedIn link can be found here: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/86391297>.

Figure 22: LinkedIn account

The BIOSYSMO LinkedIn profile, which now reached 120 followers, has been created to disseminate the project results to professionals through creating a network of connections from the environmental sector, academia, media, general public, as well as companies and relevant stakeholders.

¹ <https://datareportal.com/social-media-users>

² <https://www.mindtools.com/am8a1fv/how-to-use-linkedin-effectively>

4.1.1 LinkedIn target audiences

LinkedIn³ is a social network which allows making valuable connections with people on similar fields of expertise. LinkedIn is mainly a platform for professionals to spread awareness and inform the public. Therefore, LinkedIn targets to end-users such as environmental consultancy, engineering companies, polluting industries, plant breeders, and producers, and scientists.

4.2 Twitter account

Twitter is an online news and social networking platform, where hot and short news are made public to a wide range of subscribers. Followers of the BIOSYSMO Twitter account will be able to read posts about project’s activities, like and comment for interaction. This platform is one of the most popular social media platforms, with 100 million daily active users and 500 million tweets sent daily. Its primary purpose is to connect people and allow people to share their thoughts with a big audience⁴.

The BIOSYSMO Twitter link can be found here: <https://twitter.com/biosysmo>

Figure 23: BIOSYSMO Twitter account

4.2.1 Twitter target audiences

Twitter targets to the same audience of LinkedIn plus students, researchers and public in general. Most users are between the ages of 25 and 34, and around 40% of the users are scholars⁵.

4.3 Social media posts templates

In Figure 24 the social media posts templates are designed by the dissemination manager, EXELISIS, covering a variety of announcements. The social media posts templates are divided into 5 different designs, aiming to present project goals and impacts, host meeting announcements, team members introduction and dissemination materials design.

³ <https://blog.waalaxy.com/en/linkedin-what-is-it/>

⁴ <https://blog.hubspot.com/marketing/what-is-twitter>

⁵ <https://blog.hootsuite.com/twitter-demographics>

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(d)

Figure 24: Post Templates a. Introduction-details of the project (the image changes accordingly to the text), b. Impacts of the project, c. Meetings-Workshops-Presentations (on 3D display), d. Partners presentation (image relevant to the partner), e. Dissemination materials (3D mock-up display)

5 Conclusions

This deliverable summarises the visual identity of the BIOSYSMO project, along with the website design and development and the social media platforms launch. The BIOSYSMO logo and branding identity was designed and communicated to the project consortium and will be uniformly used in the future, in presentations, future dissemination materials, dissemination events etc. The website is a key element of the project's dissemination strategy. The website will ensure the visibility of the project, facilitate the dissemination of the project's results and promote their exploitation. Moreover, social networks presence is ensured through the creation a LinkedIn page, as well as a twitter account. The project website and its social media will continuously be updated, while adjustments will be made as the project progresses.

6 References

- [1] <https://datareportal.com/social-media-users>
- [2] <https://www.mindtools.com/am8a1fv/how-to-use-linkedin-effectively>
- [3] <https://blog.waalaxy.com/en/linkedin-what-is-it/>
- [4] <https://blog.hubspot.com/marketing/what-is-twitter>
- [5] <https://blog.hootsuite.com/twitter-demographics>